

RAMAN-LIBS ANALYSIS OF LUNAR ANALOG ROCKS WITH A PORTABLE HANDHELD INSTRUMENT: IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

A. G. Moral^{1(*)}, I. Drozdovskiy², C. P. Canora¹, J. Zafra¹, P. Rodriguez¹, M. Benito¹, O. Prieto-Ballesteros³, A. de Dios-Cubillas³, E. Losantos⁴, J.A. Manrique⁵, G. Lopez-Reyes⁵, I. Hutchinson⁶, H. Lerman⁶, M. McHugh⁶, A. J. Ball⁷

¹INTA (Ctra.Torrejón - Ajalvir km 4, 28850 Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain)

²Directorate of Human and Robotic Exploration, European Space Agency (ESA/EAC), Cologne, Germany

³Centro de Astrobiología-CSIC-INTA (28850 Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain)

⁴Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (28760 Tres Cantos, Spain)

⁵Universidad de Valladolid. Av. Francisco Valles, 8. (47152 Valladolid, Spain)

⁶University of Leicester, Leicester, United Kingdom,

⁷Directorate of Human and Robotic Exploration, European Space Agency (ESA/ESTEC), Noordwijk, The Netherlands

(*) corresponding author: moralia@inta.es

Introduction: Within the framework of the different programmes, ESA ExPeRT (Exploration Preparation, Research and Technology) has long prioritised the development of advanced exploration technologies for both human and robotics surface exploration missions. In parallel with these technological objectives, the ESA PANGAEA (Planetary Analogue Geological and Astrobiological Exercise for Astronauts) [1], has focused on equipping future explorers with the mineralogical and geochemical expertise required for effective lunar Extravehicular Activities (EVA).

Within this scope, under ESA contract [4000138579/22/NL/AT], the Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA) has coordinated and technically led the development of two portable and handheld prototypes for ESA's PANGAEA programme, through the PHOENIX (Portable Handheld cOmbinEd RamaN-LIBS-XRF) project [2]. The overarching goal is to enable fast, unambiguous *in-situ* determination of the chemical and molecular composition of lunar rocks – a capability equally valuable for suited astronauts and for future robotic landers or rovers. The project also focuses on optimising the Human-Machine Interface (HMI) for operation under realistic lunar constraints, including dust, harsh lighting, and EVA suit limitations.

The PHOENIX for PANGAEA project output: The project successfully developed, delivered to ESA and tested two different technology-demonstration breadboards (TRL 4): the BB1, which combines Raman and LIBS techniques, and the BB2, combining Raman and XRF techniques. In this way, each instrument thus covers the acquisition of information on the elemental (LIBS or XRF) and molecular (Raman) composition for comprehensive analysis of the different lunar rocks.

Additionally, both devices feature an integrated RGB imaging camera to facilitate precise spot

selection in video mode (down to 100 microns) and provide visual context for each measurement spot as high-resolution macro-imaging allowing to complement spectra with sample 2D colour, and texture.

Both breadboards allow wireless control and real-time data interpretation and transfer via a tablet-based Ground Support Equipment (GSE).

The Raman-LIBS instrument (BB1) — Design and Operations: The BB1 instrument (Figure 1) is designed to complete a full analytical sequence in under two minutes: the operator selects the analysis point on the sample using the camera's video feed, the instrument captures a contextual pre-analysis image, performs Raman and LIBS measurements on the same spot, and finally records a post-analysis image to verify any laser-induced sample alteration. Control and initial data evaluation are handled via the wireless GSE tablet, which features a user-friendly interface optimised for EVA suit constraints. Ergonomic considerations – including gloved operation, manageable size, and intuitive button layout – were integrated from the earliest design phase.

Figure 1: The BB1 prototype

Field Testing at the LUNA Facility: Raman-LIBS results: Prior to delivery, the BB1 instrument was verified in laboratory conditions, confirming its high scientific capability for lunar rock analysis [3]. Subsequently, both BB1 and BB2 underwent a comprehensive field validation campaign at LUNA – the ESA/EAC and DLR analogue facility in Cologne, Germany [4]. LUNA provides a high-

fidelity simulated lunar environment, including a large regolith simulant bed and an advanced Sun Simulator that reproduces the harsh illumination (high contrast, deep shadows) of the lunar surface.

The test campaign used a suite of high-fidelity lunar analogue rocks from the LUNA collection:

- Anorthosites (Norway) – representing lunar highland crust
- Basalts (Etna, Lanzarote) – analogous to lunar mare material
- Suevite impact breccias (Ries Crater, Germany) – matching shocked impact-basin lithologies
- Peridotite nodules – deeper mantle analogues

ESA astronaut Matthias Maurer, wearing a pressurised Atlas EVA suit simulator, performed the main operational demonstration. The campaign executed four structured scenarios:

1. Sunlit surface operations – with the Sun Simulator active at full intensity.
2. Deep shadow operations – relying solely on the instruments’ built-in LED illumination.
3. Traverse simulation – moving between ten measurement stations under strict time limits (target “Time-to-Spectrum” <3 minutes).
4. Contamination and recovery – intentionally applying regolith dust simulant to samples, then cleaning and re-measuring to assess dust resilience.

Figure 2: The BB1 instrument operated by ESA astronaut Matthias Maurer at the ESA-DLR LUNA analogue facility. *Credit: ESA/EAC LAMB team*

Ergonomics for EVA and Performance in Challenging Environments: A central focus was evaluating instrument usability under EVA suit constraints. Suited operations, with gloves and restricted mobility, provided critical feedback on:

- First-attempt success rates for acquiring valid spectra with gloved hands
- Ability to recover from measurement errors within two minutes
- Display readability under extreme sunlit and shadow conditions

- Effectiveness of cleaning procedures after dust contamination

The challenging lighting – simulating direct lunar sunlight (high intensity, sharp shadows) – tested the tablet display’s visibility and the operator’s ability to align the instrument’s measurement spot. In deep shadow, the built-in LED illumination proved sufficient for both camera targeting and safe operation, though display brightness required optimization.

The dusty environment simulation revealed that regolith contamination on optical windows and sample surfaces could degrade spectral quality. However, cleaning BB1 equipped with brushes was not required. Nonetheless, to maintain instrument performance in longer EVA some design improvements are needed for future flight models (e.g., protective covers, simplified field cleaning).

Results and Lessons Learned: The BB1 instrument successfully acquired high-quality Raman and LIBS spectra from all analogue rock types under both sunlit and shadow conditions, with “Time-to-Spectrum” consistently below the three-minute target. First-attempt success rates exceeded 75% for gloved operation after initial familiarization.

In the presentation of this work, we will show both the representative scientific results achievable with this combined Raman-LIBS instrument, and the lessons learned regarding the ergonomics of this type of instrumentation, how to facilitate operation for an astronaut equipped with their suit; or the influence that lunar restrictions can impose on the mode of operation for the optimization of scientific return on the surface of the Moon. These insights directly support ESA’s future lunar exploration programmes.

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by ESA contract 4000138579/22/NL/AT, and MCIN PID2022-142490OB-C31/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 project.

Special thanks to the entire LUNA DLR team and EAC/ESA for their support and assistance in carrying out the LUNA test campaign; and especially M. Maurer for his time and valuable advice on improving the future operation of this type of instrument.

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